

Helping Dyslexia Children Succeed in Primary Schools

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Abstract

The topic of this paper is titled 'helping dyslexia children succeed in primary schools'. It is a theoretical paper. Dyslexia is one of the learning disabilities among children in primary schools and it poses serious academic problems on the affected ones. According to the researchers, some of the observable classroom problems of dyslexia children include: having difficulties in learning the names and sounds of letters, experiencing difficulties in learning spelling that is unpredictable and inconsistent, putting letters and figures the wrong way round, experiencing confusion with the order of letters in words when writing, reads slowly and usually make errors while reading aloud, answers questions well orally but finds it difficult to write the answers down, and having difficulty in carrying out a sequence of directions. They also have a limited understanding of nonverbal communication, employ work avoidance tactics, easily distracted, withdrawn and always tired due to amount of concentration and effort required in accomplishing a task. The researchers however, indicated the likely consequences of these problems on these children which include: frustration, poor social relationship, inconsistencies in performances, anxiety, poor self image, depression and family problems. Also, ways of helping them succeed in school through teachers are highlighted as follows: being loving and patience with them, giving them more time in accomplishing reading, writing and spelling tasks, being consistent with them, making use of different colours of chalks in overcoming problem of copying notes from the chalk board and breaking school tasks into bits to overcome the difficulty in keeping sequence of instructions. Then, Conclusion, recommendations and references are highlighted.

Key words: *Dyslexia, Counselling, Problems, Consequences, Ways of succeeding in school*

Introduction

Dyslexia is one of the learning disabilities among children in primary schools. American Academy of Pediatrics (2011), opines that learning disabilities are refer to as a number of disorders which may affect the acquisition, organization, retention, understanding or use of verbal or non-verbal information by a child. For the researchers, learning disabilities are hidden problems or disorders that set some children back from learning at the same pace with their mates in school and dyslexia is one of them. Ordinarily; one may not identify a child with dyslexia until such a child enters school. According to the National Institutes of Health, up to 15% of the U.S.

population is suffering from this problem (Bhandari, 2015). This problem is not restricted for the people of western world only. It has been observed that some African children are also experiencing such difficulty because it is an issue that is globally.

However, Dyslexia can occur at any level of intellectual ability. A child with learning disabilities begins school expecting to learn and be successful. If a child is having difficulty in school such as being dyslexia, she may learn differently from other kids. It is usually the parents that are often the first to notice that something doesn't seem right with their child but sometimes find it difficult to solve the problem due to ignorance of what is happening and where to seek for succour. In school, these children may be suffering from emotional problem and anxiety as a result of some labelling they may be getting from their teachers and school mates such as dullard, fool, good for nothing child to mention a few as a result of the problem which they are not the cause. Some teachers may be ignorant of this problem too, or even if they are aware, may not know how to help them out.

Therefore, there is a need that this disorder should be looked into, stating its problems on the children, consequences and providing possible ways the children could be helped to succeed in school.

CONCEPTS Concept of Dyslexia

Dyslexia is a chronic problem with reading. It is a common learning difficulty, affecting a large percentage of those identified as learning disabled (Bhandari 2015). Dyslexia is a learning disability that makes it hard to read, write and spell. Dyslexia is also called specific reading disability and reading disorder (Grigorenko, 2007). However, Lindsay (2000) sees dyslexia as a combination of abilities and difficulties which affect the learning process in one or more of reading, spelling and writing.

Concept of Counselling

Counselling according to Fakunle (2011) is a professional assistance offered to an individual by a trained counselling psychologist to help the individual solve his developmental and adjustment problem. For, Olujinmi & Olubukola (2014), counselling is a professional and confidential relationship between a Guidance Counsellor and a client, that is facilitated in order to find a lasting solution to the challenge of the client that is beyond his capacity. Counselling for this study is seen as a careful guided professional help being rendered by a trained Counsellor to his client who is being confronted with a challenge that is likely preventing him from reaching his life potentials. This indicates that any life challenges an individual is passing through can be handled through counselling. Therefore, the presence of dyslexics in the class room poses a lot of challenges to their teachers and there is need that counsellors should step in towards finding a way of eliminating these challenges.

Causes of Dyslexia

Experts do not know for sure what causes dyslexia but it often runs in families. So it may be passed from parents to children (genetic disorder (American Academy of Pediatrics, 2011). Also, some studies have found problems with how the brain links letters and words with the sounds they make. Dyslexia occurs because the brain jumbles and mixes up letters and words. This is why children with dyslexia often has a poor memory of spoken and written words (Noble & Mccandliss, 2005).Dyslexia is not caused by poor vision and people with dyslexia do not see letters backwards (American Academy of Pediatrics, 2011).

Observable problems of Dyslexia Children in the Class Rooms

Problems confronting dyslexia child in school differ from one child to another. Panda and Msbucks (2013) stated the problems to include: having difficulties in learning the names and sounds of letters, experiencing difficulties in learning spelling that is unpredictable and inconsistent, and putting letters and figures the wrong way round, example: putting 6 instead of 9. For Marshall (2004), dyslexia child faces confusion with the order of letters in words when writing, reads slowly and usually make errors while reading aloud, have visual disturbances when reading (the letters or the words may seem to be moving in the sight of the child or appeared blurred), answers questions well orally but finds it difficult to write the answers down, and also having difficulty in carrying out a sequence of directions.

Moreover, children with dyslexia appear slow in processing spoken and or written words, experience poor concentration, are confused with letters that are similar, hesitates in reading, shows confusion with numerical order, experiences difficulty in learning to tell time, date or months of the year (Lindsay,2000). They also have a limited understanding of nonverbal communication, employ work avoidance tactics, is easily distracted, withdrawn and always tired due to amount of concentration and effort required in accomplishing a task (BDA Management Board (2009). Linking letters with sounds, confusing small words such as at & to, writing words backwards such as tips for pits are among their problems (Tannock, 2009). The above problems have serious consequences both social and emotional on a particular child who is dyslexia.

Consequences of these problems on the Children

The impact of dyslexia on an individual child depends on the severity of the cluster of the problems he is experiencing. However; the following are the consequences.

Frustration

The frustration of a child with dyslexia seems to be centred on the child's inability to meet expectations. There is a likelihood that parents and teachers can be seeing the child as a bright and enthusiastic person who is not learning how to read and write. According to Marshall (2004), he opines that now and then teachers keep on reporting that the child is smart and bright if he would put j more effort but no one knows how much effort the child is putting. The pain of not meeting expectations makes a dyslexic not to achieve his goals in life. Researchers are of the opinion that this problem will likely cause the child to develop perfectionist expectations in order

to deal with the I anxiety and the child will grow up believing that to make a mistake is terrible in life (Ryan,2013).The silly mistakes dyslexic makes in class is frustrating that the child will be feeling inadequate.

Poor Social Relationship

The above is also another consequence of dyslexia. Panda & Msbucks (2013) state that such children frequently have problems with social relationships because judging from their class room problems, j they may be physically and socially immature in comparison to their peers which may lead to a poor j self-image and less peer acceptance. Their social immaturity may make them appear awkward in j social situations. However; since dyslexia affects oral language functioning, affected children may experience difficulty finding the right words, and may stammer or pause before answering direct questions. If this situation continues unchecked, it can put them at disadvantage as they enter adolescents when language will become more central to their relationships with peers.

Inconsistencies in Performances

Dyslexia performance fluctuates and this makes it extremely difficult for the individual to learn to compensate because one cannot predict the intensity of the symptoms on a given day (Tannock, 2009). j This inconsistency of dyslexics may produce serious challenges in their lives if unchecked. It is true that everyone has strengths and weaknesses but that of dyslexics exaggerates.

Anxiety

The dyslexics suffer from anxiety. Dyslexics appear fearful because of their constant frustration and confusion in school. These feelings, according to Ryan, (2013), are exacerbated by the inconsistencies of dyslexics because they may anticipate failure and entering new situations can become extremely anxiety provoking. This is because anxiety may cause one to avoid whatever frightens him and as a result some teachers and parents may misinterpret this avoidance to mean laziness. Probably, this seems to be one of the reasons why some dyslexics hesitate from participating in some school activities like home work.

Poor Self-Image

The dyslexic's self-image appears to be vulnerable to frustration and anxiety. According to Erikson's theory on child development during the first years of school, every child must resolve the conflicts between a positive self-image and feelings of inferiority. If children succeed in school, they will develop positive feelings about themselves and believe that they can succeed in life. If they meet failure and frustration, they learn that they are inferior to others and that their effort makes very little difference. Instead of feeling powerful and productive, they learn that their environment controls them. They feel powerless and incompetent. According to Ryan (2013), researchers have learned that when learners succeed, they credit their own efforts for their success but when they fail, they tell themselves to try harder. However, when the dyslexics succeeds, he

is likely to attribute the success to luck but if he fails, he will see himself as stupid. This is more reason something must be done to help them succeed in school.

Depression

The above is another impact of dyslexia and it seems to be frequent. Children with this learning disability are at higher risk for intense feelings of sorrow and pain (BDA Management Board (2009). Some of them may turn their anger towards themselves because of their low self-esteem. A depressed child may misbehave in order to cover up his painful feelings. Ryan (2013) opines that children who are depressed tend to have the following three characteristics:

Firstly, they tend to have negative thoughts about themselves, which is a negative self-image. Secondly, they tend to view the world negatively. They are less likely to enjoy the positive experiences in life. This makes it difficult for them to have fun.

Finally, they have trouble imagining anything positive about the future. The depressed dyslexic experiences great pain in his present condition and also foresees a life of continuing failure.

Induces Family Problems

Dyslexia being one of the invisible disabilities has a tremendous consequence on the child's family. It causes siblings rivalry. Non dyslexia children will often feel jealous of the child who is getting the majority of the parents' attention, time and money. And this attention increases the chances that the dyslexic child will be acting negatively against the achieving children in the family (Ryan, 2013).

A child that is witnessing a cluster of these problems and consequences together may find it very difficult to succeed in life. This type of children cannot be left behind in their educational pursuit. This is because every child that comes to school wants to succeed despite their peculiar challenges facing them. Therefore counselling services will be extended to teachers for them to know and learn the management of dyslexia child for success in school.

Need For Dyslexia Counselling

The importance of counselling as a way out for human challenges therefore cannot be over emphasizing throughout the world. Children with this disorder possess capability necessary for greater achievement but perform at a level far below their capacity. Sometimes they appear to their teachers and parents as those kids that lack motivation or not to be trying hard enough. Dyslexia may be accompanied by, but is not as a result of lack of motivation, emotional or behavioural problems, and sensory impairment (Bhandari, 2015). If children are ignored to grow up to become adult with these learning disabilities, it will become a lifelong issue unfortunately, if not fixed. Also, the children will not be fulfilled in life because they will be wallowing in anxieties and depression. Having dyslexia does not mean that a child's ability to learn is below average but not being able to read and write can cause hindrances to other areas of learning. For the teachers, they will be seeing their efforts in imparting knowledge as being wasted and also

they may become demoralised in their profession. To avoid these problems from surfacing, the present researchers conceptualised the topic of this write up in order for teachers to help these children out in their educational pursuit because every child that comes to school wants to succeed despite the peculiar challenges facing him.

However, in the light of the above, counselling in primary school environment will not be slated to the pupils alone. Counselling should be extended to their teachers too. Counsellors can organise programmes such as workshops and seminars in order to educate the teachers on strategies through which these dyslexia children can be helped to succeed in school. A child that is experiencing five or more of the problems indicated above can never succeed in school and also in life if deaf attention is paid to the child's problems. The child will lack confidence, have emotional problems such as depression, aggression and anxiety, become frustrated and can even resort to school dropout as a result of constant failure in school work. In the words of Moody, (2010), the child will not know who he is. The child will become tensed up. Aston, (2014) opines that aggressive and anti-social behaviours may result from these tensions. Counsellors should therefore guide teachers as follows:

Being Loving and Patience with the Dyslexia Children

Teachers should be made to understand the need to be loving and patient with dyslexia children. The availability of a dyslexia child in the class is frustrating but teachers should endure and have patient with the child for he is not the cause of his problem. This atmosphere will enhance his being comfortable in the class, develop confidence and also boost his self esteem.

Giving the Children More Time to Finish Reading, Writing and Spelling Tasks

The above three disabilities will affect a child's ability to demonstrate what he has learnt in the areas of knowledge. Teachers should know that children with these problems will need more time to finish a reading, writing and spelling task. This is why they often fail whenever a timed work is being given. Teachers should therefore put in additional time on daily basis on any of the above tasks. This may appear boring but this is a sacrifice that can be made for the child to succeed in school.

Being Consistent with dyslexia Child

This implies that there is a likelihood of teachers subjecting most of the tasks in the class room to repetition so that the dyslexia child will connect. Carefulness should be applied here by teachers so that they will know when to allow the children a break time especially when a particular skill become stabilised.

Making Use of Different Colours of Chalks in overcoming Problem of Copying Notes from the Chalk Board

Teachers should help the children by using different colour of chalks for each line if there is a lot of written information on the board or underline every second line with a different coloured chalk

(Hodge, 2000). This will help in drawing the attention of the child to the order of letters, and to also know where one line ends and where another starts while copying notes. Teachers will be made to know the need to be spacing their writings well and to leave the notes for a longer time for them to be able to finish.

Breaking School Tasks into Bits to Overcome the Difficulty in Keeping Sequence of Instructions

There is also need that teachers should be made to have clear understanding of this problem of dyslexia within the classroom in order not to misunderstand their behaviours. Hodge (2000) asserts that having understanding of what poor auditory short term memory can cause in terms of retaining input from the teacher is of great importance. A child with this problem will find it very difficult to remember even a short list of instruction. Teachers should therefore see the need to break school tasks into bits so that the child will be able to remember the pieces of information easily and also acts on it.

Conclusion

From this study, one can see the problems and consequences facing dyslexia among primary school children. And for these children to succeed in school and in life there is a need for a change. Therefore to effect these changes, Guidance Counsellors and teachers are seen as the major instruments through which the needed changes can be effected in the lives of the children.

Recommendation

For the teachers to achieve effective change in the lives of dyslexics in the classroom, government should be organising workshops and seminars for the teachers through the Guidance Counsellors so that guidelines on how to be handling these dyslexia children will be imparted to them.

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